

Changes of Extreme Air Temperature in Jerusalem

Joseph Nowarski, M.Sc., ME – Energy Conservation Expert

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Abstract

The annual minimum air temperature in Jerusalem increases with years. From 1993 to 2019, the minimum temperature increased by 1.47°C from -0.46°C to 1.01°C. Considering the current linear trendline, in year 2100 the minimum yearly temperature in Jerusalem will be 5.60°C, 6.06°C above year 1993 level.

Also daily changes of daily average temperature increased significantly. The maximum negative change (getting colder the next day) increased from -7.98°C in year 1993 to -10.72°C in year 2019. According to the linear trendline, in year 2100 the maximum daily change will be -19.26°C.

This work analyses 7 parameters of extreme temperature or extreme temperature changes, based on over 1 million air temperature records monitored at one meteorological station in Jerusalem.

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1. Source of Data

The Israeli Meteorological Service publishes on Internet monitored records of various meteorological parameters from many meteorological stations across the country [2]. The Israeli Meteorological Service is governmental unit.

The data can be downloaded to CSV (Text and Excel) files. The records are for every 10 minutes, which results in very big files. Number of records for one year is 52,560. There are limits of downloaded file's size, allowing download of one parameter for one year only.

This work applies over 1 million air temperature records monitored at one meteorological station in Jerusalem, based on publication "*Dynamic Trendline of Air Temperature in Jerusalem*" [1].

The parameter selected is "temperature", which is "dry temperature".

There are few meteorological station is Jerusalem. Among all Jerusalem stations, Givat Ram station number 7020 has the longest database, reaching year 1993, therefore it was selected for the purpose of this work. Givat Ram is in the center of Jerusalem, the site of Jerusalem University, government campus, the parliament and Israel Museum. The station is located at the Institute of Earth Science at Jerusalem University, N31.7704° E35.1973°, elevation 770 m. This station may be regarded as "open air" without higher buildings around, surrounded by relatively green area.

There is very large number of missing records for years 2001-2003. Therefore, this work does not include years 2001-2003.

In addition some records are missing also in other years. Following procedure is applied for determination of the missing records:

- Up to 11 missing records, the estimation is done as linear interpolation between the neighboring records.
- Application of records for the relevant dates and times from other stations in Jerusalem (Givat Shaul and Jerusalem Center) using correction coefficients.

- If no data from any alternative station is available, records from neighboring days are applied, as an average between day before and day after the missing period.

366 days' years have colder average temperature than 365 days' years, because of an additional day in winter. Therefore 29 February was removed from the calculations.

The "year" starts on 1 January 00:00 and ends on 31 December 23:50.

All data are in degrees Celsius according to winter time – LST.

The dates are in format dd/mm.

2. Minimum Yearly Temperature

The minimum yearly temperature is calculated as a minimum of all records for the same year.

Chart 1 - Minimum Yearly Temperature [°C]

Trendline formula:

$$Temp [^{\circ}C] = 0.05663717 * x - 0.52123894$$

x is tick number starting with 1993 as tick number 1.

Table 1 - Minimum Yearly Temperature

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	-0.46	0.00
2000	-0.07	0.40
2019	1.01	1.47
2030	1.63	2.10
2050	2.76	3.23
2075	4.18	4.64
2100	5.60	6.06
yearly	0.057	

Yearly increase of the minimum temperature is 0.057°C.

From year 1993 to 2019, the minimum temperature increased by 1.47°C from -0.46°C to 1.01° C. This may explain that snow, which once was almost every year in Jerusalem, now is very rear.

Considering the current linear trendline, in year 2100 the minimum yearly temperature in Jerusalem will be 5.60°C, 6.06°C above year 1993 level.

Chart 2 - Day of the Minimum Yearly Temperature

The day of minimum temperature was in the past in February, now moving towards January and December, which means that February is not so cold anymore as it was in the past.

Table 2 - Day of the Minimum Yearly Temperature

Min	13/12
Ave	28/01
Max	15/03

3. Maximum Yearly Temperature

The maximum yearly temperature is calculated as a maximum of all records for the same year.

Chart 3 - Maximum Yearly Temperature [°C]

Trendline formula:

$$Temp [°C] = 0.02610619 * x + 36.59646018$$

Table 3 - Maximum Yearly Temperature

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	36.62	0.00
2000	36.81	0.18
2019	37.30	0.68
2030	37.59	0.97
2050	38.11	1.49
2075	38.76	2.14
2100	39.42	2.79
yearly	0.026	

The yearly increase of the maximum yearly temperature is much lower than minimum yearly temperature, about half.

Chart 4 - Day of the Maximum Yearly Temperature

The highest yearly temperature is moving from July to May.

Table 4 - Day of the Maximum Yearly Temperature

Min	16/05
Ave	06/07
Max	10/09

4. Difference between Maximum and Minimum Yearly Temperature

Chart 5 - Difference between Maximum and Minimum Yearly Temperature

Table 5 - Difference between Maximum and Minimum Yearly Temperature

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	37.09	0.00
2000	36.87	-0.21
2019	36.29	-0.79
2030	35.96	-1.13
2050	35.35	-1.74
2075	34.58	-2.50
2100	33.82	-3.27
yearly	-0.031	

The reason for decreasing difference is the higher increase of the minimum temperature than of the maximum temperature.

5. Difference between Daily Maximum and Minimum Temperature

5.1. Minimum

The minimum is calculated as the year minimum of the difference between daily maximum and minimum temperature.

Chart 6 - Difference between Daily Maximum and Minimum Temperature - Minimum

Table 6 - Difference between Daily Maximum and Minimum Temperature - Minimum

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	2.02	0.00
2000	1.93	-0.09
2019	1.69	-0.33
2030	1.55	-0.48
2050	1.29	-0.73
2075	0.97	-1.05
2100	0.65	-1.38
yearly	-0.013	

5.2. Average

The average is calculated as the year average of the difference between daily maximum and minimum temperature.

Chart 7 - Difference between Daily Maximum and Minimum Temperature - Average

Table 7 - Difference between Daily Maximum and Minimum Temperature - Average

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	8.31	0.00
2000	8.42	0.11
2019	8.72	0.41
2030	8.90	0.59
2050	9.22	0.91
2075	9.62	1.31
2100	10.02	1.71
yearly	0.016	

5.3. Maximum

The maximum is calculated as the year maximum of the difference between daily maximum and minimum temperature.

Chart 8 - Difference between Daily Maximum and Minimum Temperature - Maximum

Table 8 - Difference between Daily Maximum and Minimum Temperature - Maximum

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	17.45	0.00
2000	17.62	0.16
2019	18.06	0.60
2030	18.31	0.86
2050	18.77	1.32
2075	19.35	1.90
2100	19.93	2.48
yearly	0.023	

6. Daily Changes of Minimum Temperature

6.1. Maximum Negative Change

"Negative" means getting colder the next day.

Chart 9 - Daily Changes of Minimum Temperature – Maximum Negative Change

Table 9 - Daily Changes of Minimum Temperature - Maximum Negative Change

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	-9.17	0.00
2000	-9.39	-0.22
2019	-10.00	-0.83
2030	-10.35	-1.19
2050	-11.00	-1.83
2075	-11.80	-2.63
2100	-12.60	-3.44
yearly	-0.032	

Chart 10 - Day of the highest minimum temperature drop

Year 2012 was removed from this analysis, as in this year the drop was unusually low (-5.7°C).

Table 10 - Day of the highest minimum temperature drop

Min	10/02
Ave	10/04
Max	12/05

6.2. Maximum Positive Change

"Positive" means getting warmer the next day.

Chart 11 - Daily Changes of Minimum Temperature – Maximum Positive Change

Table 11 - Daily Changes of Minimum Temperature – Maximum Positive Change

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	8.44	0.00
2000	8.40	-0.04
2019	8.27	-0.17
2030	8.20	-0.24
2050	8.08	-0.36
2075	7.92	-0.52
2100	7.76	-0.68
yearly	-0.006	

7. Daily Changes of Average Temperature

7.1. Maximum Negative Change

Chart 12 - Daily Changes of Average Temperature - Maximum Negative Change

Trendline formula:

$$\Delta T [^{\circ}\text{C}] = -0.105440327 * x - 7.873227528$$

Table 12 - Daily Changes of Average Temperature - Maximum Negative Change

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	-7.98	0.00
2000	-8.72	-0.74
2019	-10.72	-2.74
2030	-11.88	-3.90
2050	-13.99	-6.01
2075	-16.62	-8.65
2100	-19.26	-11.28
yearly	-0.105	

Chart 13 - Day of the highest average temperature drop

There is no change of the average day of the highest average temperature drop, which is 6 April.

Table 13 - Day of the highest average temperature drop

Min	31/01
Ave	06/04
Max	19/05

7.2. Maximum Positive Change

Chart 14 - Daily Changes of Average Temperature - Maximum Positive Change

Table 14 - Daily Changes of Average Temperature - Maximum Positive Change

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	7.44	0.00
2000	7.14	-0.30
2019	6.33	-1.11
2030	5.86	-1.58
2050	5.01	-2.43
2075	3.94	-3.50
2100	2.88	-4.56
yearly	-0.043	

8. Daily Changes of Maximum Temperature

8.1. Maximum Negative Change

Chart 15 - Daily Changes of Maximum Temperature - Maximum Negative Change

Table 15 - Daily Changes of Maximum Temperature - Maximum Negative Change

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	-12.71	0.00
2000	-12.90	-0.19
2019	-13.41	-0.70
2030	-13.71	-1.00
2050	-14.25	-1.54
2075	-14.93	-2.22
2100	-15.60	-2.89
yearly	-0.027	

8.2. Maximum Positive Change

Chart 16 - Daily Changes of Maximum Temperature - Maximum Positive Change

Daily changes of maximum temperature are decreasing. The change is -0.050°C per year, in average.

Table 16 - Daily Changes of Maximum Temperature - Maximum Positive Change

year	°C	to 1993 °C
1993	9.27	0.00
2000	8.92	-0.35
2019	7.97	-1.30
2030	7.42	-1.85
2050	6.42	-2.85
2075	5.17	-4.10
2100	3.92	-5.35
yearly	-0.050	

9. References

1. Dynamic Trendline of Air Temperature in Jerusalem, Joseph Nowarski,
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